

Evidence of a 12,800-year-old Shallow Airburst Depression in Louisiana with Large Deposits of Shocked Quartz and Melted Materials

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FIGURES

Figure S1. Sand grain analysis for Trench 1. The stratum centered at 70 cm (range: 77-62 cm) displays nearly double the concentration of 40-μm diameter silt.

Figure S2. Microspherule and meltglass distribution in the material deposits. An analysis of ~100 microspherules shows diameters ranging from ~1 to 65 µm, averaging 14 µm. Meltglass fragments were typically larger than a few mm.

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Fig. S3. Original version of Fig. 17A-F in the main manuscript.

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Fig. S4. Original version of Fig. 17A-F in the main manuscript.

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Fig. S5. Original version of Fig. 17A-F in the main manuscript.

Fig. S6. Original version of Fig. 17G-L in the main manuscript.

Fig. S7. Original version of Fig. 17G-L in the main manuscript.

Fig. S8. Original version of Fig. 17G-L in the main manuscript.

Fig. S9. Original version of Fig. 18A-F in the main manuscript.

Fig. S10. Original version of Fig. 18A-F in the main manuscript.

Fig. S11. Original version of Fig. 18A-F in the main manuscript.

Fig. S12. Original version of Fig. 18G-L in the main manuscript.

Fig. S13. Original version of Fig. 18A-F in the main manuscript.

Fig. S14. Original version of Fig. 18A-F in the main manuscript.

Fig. S15. Original version of Fig. 26 in the main manuscript. (A)-(D) Portions of quartz grains are isotropic under crossed polars ("M") and were subsequently identified as melted quartz using CL. Glass-filled planar fractures (PF) and non-planar fractures (nPF) are marked.

Fig. S16. Original version of Fig. 27 in the main manuscript. (A-F) SEM-BSE, EPI-PPL, and SEM-CL images of incipient micro-brecciated grains. Panel E is an SEM-CL image indicating that the glass-filled micro-brecciated grain in panel D is non-luminescent (black) and, therefore, amorphous.

TABLES

Table S1. Radiocarbon dates. Seventeen dates were acquired, of which eight were usable. Nine were excluded because of insufficient carbon, young carbon, or old carbon.

Date	Lab #	Description	14 C age	±	Cal BP	±	Depth	Material	Age range
		Woodland			1250	250	7.5	Trench 1, projectile point	1500 1000
		Early Archaic			9000	1000	48	Trench 1, projectile point	10000 8000
10/18/2021	D-AMS 043969	210903-D-01	10775	43	12739	18	60-75	Carbon from glass and MSp peak	12810 12692
5/7/2020	D-AMS 037679	Perk P-20	25062	98	29335	176	114	Bulk sed	29735 29090
1/23/2024	UGAMS-67351	Perk FTB A1,A2,C	8970	35	10114	93	Surface	Carbon in meltglass, Pond	10232 9916
5/7/2020	D-AMS 037682	Vee, Perk V-19	10554	42	12580	68	Surface	Carbon in meltglass, Vee	12687 12481
3/16/2024	UGAMS-68225	Pond, Cat-1	10660	35	12684	36	Surface	Carbon in meltglass, Pond	12730 12621
3/16/2024	UGAMS-68226	Pond, Cat-2	12100	40	13960	78	Surface	Carbon in meltglass, Pond	14078 13810
1/23/2024	UGAMS-67350	Perk Layr-4	16850	65	20369	83	Surface	Carbon in meltglass, Pond	20522 20198
2/21/2025	UGASM-74596	Perkins-sp	24110	120	28270	204	Surface	Carbon, CSp from Pond meltglass	28059 28509
2/21/2025	UGASM-74595	Perkins-wo	42200	1250	45265	1252	Surface	Carbon, from Pond	43936 45989
8/31/2021	UCIAMS-250412	Perk CAT-2	52800	1800	53117	1347	Surface	Carbon, fm Pond 'breccia' pile	
8/31/2021	UCIAMS-250413	Perk CAT-3	>54000	--	>54000		Surface	Carbon, fm Pond 'breccia' pile	
8/31/2021	UCIAMS-250411	Perk CAT-1	>54700	--	>54700		Surface	Carbon, fm Pond 'breccia' pile	
8/31/2021	UCIAMS-250414	Perk CAT-4	>56000	--	>56000		Surface	Carbon, fm Pond 'breccia' pile	
5/7/2020	D-AMS 037681	Perk W4-9			N/A			Insufficient carbon	
5/7/2020	D-AMS 037680	Perk W3-9	73	22	73			Carbon, lumps	

Table S2. Unmodeled and modeled Bayesian age-depth model. For Trench 1, two radiocarbon dates and two age ranges for cultural artifacts were modeled.

Perkins--P_Sequence	Unmodelled (BP)						Modelled (BP)						Amodel 106.4; Aoverall 107.2	
			95% CI		99% CI				95% CI		99% CI		A	C
Depth_Model	mu	sigma	from	to	from	to	mu	sigma	from	to	from	to		
Boundary							1228	267	1769	704	2039	438		96
C_Date Late Woodland Point	1251	250	1751	751	2001	501	1228	267	1769	704	2039	438	96.9	96
C_Date Early Archaic Point	9001	1000	11001	7001	12001	6001	9057	619	10277	7805	10818	7191	120	93
C_Date Pt/MSp/Glass peak	12786	50	12886	12686	12936	12636	12791	68	13019	12708	13028	12692	97.5	98
R_Date D-AMS 043969	12739	18	12810	12692	12833	12679	12794	69	13021	12713	13030	12697	99.5	98
R_Date D-AMS 037679	29335	176	29735	29090	29896	28957	29354	181	29777	29086	29976	28939	105	97
Boundary							29354	181	29777	29086	29976	28939		97
U(0,4)	2	1.14	4.0E-17	4	4.0E-17	4	1.00	0.59	5.4E-17	2.008	5.4E-17	2.16	100	91
Exp(1,-10,3)	1.93	1.00	-0.211	2.94	-3.05	2.94	1.94	0.98						100
Outlier_Model General							44	65	-18	236	-138	359		100

Table S3. Unmodeled Bayesian calibrated ages. We used OxCal with IntCal20 to calibrate radiocarbon dates from Trench 1, the Pond deposit, and the Vee deposit. The results overlap at 68.3%, 95.4%, and 99.7% Confidence Intervals (CI) with the proposed YDB impact age range at 99.7% CI. Two dates are older, and one is younger than the others.

Perkins--Calibrated ages	Unmodelled (BP)							
	68% CI				95% CI		99% CI	
	mu	sigma	from	to	from	to	from	to
R_Date Pond, UGAMS-67350	20350	100	20500	20250	20550	20150	20600	20050
R_Date Pond, UGAMS-68226	13950	100	14100	13850	14100	13800	14150	13750
C_Date YDB age range	12800	50	12850	12700	12900	12650	12950	12600
R_Date Trench 1, D-AMS 043969	12750	0	12800	12700	12850	12650	12850	12650
R_Date Pond, UGAMS-68225	12700	50	12750	12650	12750	12600	12750	12450
R_Date Vee, D-AMS 037682	12600	50	12700	12450	12700	12450	12750	12250
R_Date Pond, UGAMS-67351	10100	100	10250	9950	10250	9900	10250	9900

Table S4. Information for the $^{40}\text{Ar}/^{39}\text{Ar}$ dating.

Argon testing for Perkins			Corrected ¹			Intercepts ²			Blanks		
Identifier	129		^{40}Ar (Volts)	0.419369	^{40}Ar (Volts)	0.422501	^{40}Ar (Volts)	0.003171			
Sample	PerkBlock		$\pm 1\sigma$	0.001244	$\pm 1\sigma$	0.001239	$\pm 1\sigma$	0.000111			
Material	NotListed		^{39}Ar (Volts)	0.005765	^{39}Ar (Volts)	0.005724	^{39}Ar (Volts)	0.000002			
Project	Louisiana		$\pm 1\sigma$	0.000021	$\pm 1\sigma$	0.000021	$\pm 1\sigma$	0.000001			
Tag	ok		^{38}Ar (Volts)	0.000338	^{38}Ar (Volts)	0.000292	^{38}Ar (Volts)	0.000002			
N	01		$\pm 1\sigma$	0.000003	$\pm 1\sigma$	0.000002	$\pm 1\sigma$	0.000001			
Power	W	10	^{37}Ar (Volts)	0.007686	^{37}Ar (Volts)	0.007638	^{37}Ar (Volts)	0.000002			
Age	(Ma)	0.58880897	$\pm 1\sigma$	0.000034	$\pm 1\sigma$	0.000034	$\pm 1\sigma$	0.000001			
$\pm 1\sigma$	(Ma)	1.15671471	^{36}Ar (Volts)	0.001405	^{36}Ar (Volts)	0.001365	^{36}Ar (Volts)	0.000010			
K/Ca		0.16555364	$\pm 1\sigma$	0.000006	$\pm 1\sigma$	0.000006	$\pm 1\sigma$	0.000001			
$\pm 1\sigma$		0.00095117					RunDate	09/12/24 06:24			
% ^{40}Ar	(%)	0.27539249					Δt^3	(days) 33.93342593			
$^{40}\text{Ar}^*/^{39}\text{Ar}_k$		0.2006531					J	0.001627			
K ₂ O	(wt. %)	0					$\pm 1\sigma$	0			
Sensitivity	V/fa	1E-17					^{39}Ar Decay	1.000239			
$^{39}\text{Ar}/^{40}\text{Ar}$		0.01372491					^{37}Ar Decay	1.949778			
$^{36}\text{Ar}/^{40}\text{Ar}$		0.00334019					$(^{40}\text{Ar}/^{39}\text{Ar})_k$	0.000540			
							$\pm 1\sigma$	0.000140			
							$(^{38}\text{Ar}/^{39}\text{Ar})_k$	0.012100			
							$\pm 1\sigma$	0.000050			
							$(^{37}\text{Ar}/^{39}\text{Ar})_k$	0.000000			
							$\pm 1\sigma$	0.000000			
							$(^{39}\text{Ar}/^{37}\text{Ar})_{Ca}$	0.000695			
							$\pm 1\sigma$	0.000018			
							$(^{38}\text{Ar}/^{37}\text{Ar})_{Ca}$	0.000020			
							$\pm 1\sigma$	0.000002			
							$(^{36}\text{Ar}/^{37}\text{Ar})_{Ca}$	0.000265			
							$\pm 1\sigma$	0.000004			
							$(^{36}\text{Ar}/^{38}\text{Ar})_{Cl}$	263.000000			
							$\pm 1\sigma$	0.000000			
							Ca/K	2.320000			
							$\pm 1\sigma$	0.000000			
							Cl/K	0.227000			
							$\pm 1\sigma$	0.000000			
							J	0.001626838			
							$\pm 1\sigma$	0			

Table S5. Abundances of spherules (MSp) and meltglass (MG) at 9 Perkins site locations.

Pit #1					Pit #3					Well #31--NW					Well #32--W					Walkway		
Mid	MSp/kg	MG/kg			Mid	MSp#	MSp/kg	MG#	MG/kg	Mid-cm	MSp#	MSp/kg	MG#	MG/kg	Mid-cm	MSp#	MSp/kg	MG#	MG/kg	Mid-cm	MSp/kg	MG/kg
35	0				115	2	7	0	0	5	0	0	0	0	8	0	0	0	0	15	2200	800
45	0				125	0	0	0	0	15	0	0	0	0	23	0	0	0	0	45	2000	750
55	0				135	1	50	0	0	25	0	0	0	0	38	0	0	0	0	76	500	250
65	15	0			145	0	0	0	0	35	0	0	0	0	53	0	0	0	0	106	0	0
75	0	0			155	1	50	0	0	45	0	0	0	0	69	0	0	0	0	137	0	0
85	15	0			165	0	0	0	0	55	0	0	0	0	84	19	250	1	15	167	0	0
95	0	0			175	2	55	1	25	65	0	0	0	0	99	1	15	3	40	198	0	0
105	0	0			185	3	80	3	80	75	0	0	0	0	114	0	0	0	0			
115	0	0			195	2	55	2	55	85	0	0	0	0	129	0	0	0	0			
125	0	0			205	10	270	5	135	95	3	40	1	15								
135	50	0			215	0	0	0	0	105	10	130	4	50								
145	80	1			225	0	0	0	0	115	1	15	0	0								
155	0	0			235	0	0	0	0	125	0	0	0	0								
165	0									135	0	0	0	0								
										145	0	0	0	0								
										155	0	0	0	0								
Pit #4					Core, Trench 1					Wells #4l, 1, 14, boothee					Wells #6, Vee							
Mid	MSp#	MSp/kg	MG#	MG/kg	Mid-cm	MSp#	MSp/kg	MG#	MG/kg	Mid-cm	#/12g	MSp/kg	MG/kg		Mid-cm	#/10g	MSp/kg	MG#	MG/kg			
65	2	25	1	3	8	0	0	0	0	15	0	0	0	0	15		0	0	0			
75	0	0	0	0	23	0	0	0	0	45	0	0	0	0	45		0	0	0			
85	1	15	2	7	38	0	0	0	0	76	55-ShQtz	55	0		76		0	1	85			
95	0	0	1	7	53	0	0	0	0	91	0	0	0	0	106		0	0	0			
105	5	65	2	7	69	5	1200	0	0	116	0	0	0	0	137		0	0	0			
115	0	0	1	7	84	8	105	2	25	137	4	335	0		167		0	0	0			
125	1	15	3	25	99	0	0	0	0	167	2	165	0		183		0	1	85			
135	0	0	0	0	114	0	0	0	0	198	2	165	0		198		0	0	0			
145	4	50	0	0						228	9	750	0		228		0	17	1410			
155	7	90	0	0						259	12	995	50		259	9	750	30	2490			
165	20	260	9	115						289	0	0	0		289	8	670	0	0			
175	2	25	0	0						381	0	0	0		320	10	830	0	0			
185	3	40	0	0						411	0	0	0		350	13	1300	0	0			
195	0	0	0	0						442	0	0	0		381		0	0	0			
205	2	25	0	0						472	0	0	0		411		0	0	0			
215	0	0	0	0						498	65	9200	200		442		0	0	0			
225	0	0	0	0						533	0	0	0		472		0	0	0			
235	0	0	0	0						564	0	0	0		503	1	80	0	0			
185	0	0	0	0											533	less	60	0	0			
195	0	0	0	0											564	less	30	0	0			
205	0	0	0	0											594		0	0	0			
215	0	0	1	3																		
225	0	0	0	0																		

Table S6. SEM-EDS elemental abundances for spherules and meltglass from Trench 1 and the Vee deposit.

Spherules	Al	Ca	Cr	Fe	K	Mg	Mn	Na	Ni	P	S	Si	Ti
Perk B 1 sphere	0.12	0.24	0.17	74.01	0.23	0.11	0.33	0.07	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.95	0.73
Perk G area C dark	8.53	10.84	0.30	4.54	0.15	3.51	0.00	1.41	0.12	0.06	0.39	24.31	0.77
Perk G area F tiny hollow sphere	13.63	2.64	0.36	2.33	2.11	1.88	0.00	1.47	0.00	0.15	0.08	27.52	0.06
Perk G sphere 50um	14.49	1.09	0.03	1.45	2.24	0.99	0.05	2.41	0.02	0.08	0.08	28.09	0.61
Perk G Sphere B	11.03	16.08	0.23	2.48	0.67	3.58	0.00	1.79	0.00	0.00	0.24	19.82	0.72
Perk G sphere D	13.16	11.64	0.14	3.32	1.44	2.01	0.00	1.99	0.03	0.13	0.25	20.13	1.59
Perk Spheres 56	2.63	10.72	0.10	3.40	0.12	0.50	0.00	0.34	0.16	0.00	14.87	16.93	0.44
Spher 37	2.84	8.14	0.00	2.09	0.24	0.76	0.35	0.04	0.00	0.00	12.84	19.99	2.27
Sphere 41	2.99	8.93	0.06	3.36	0.00	1.01	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.53	23.17	7.75	0.28
Sphere 53	4.14	11.15	0.01	4.20	0.26	0.85	0.41	0.28	0.15	0.11	22.36	5.02	0.92
AVG	7.36	8.15	0.14	10.12	0.75	1.52	0.11	0.98	0.05	0.11	7.43	17.05	0.84
Meltglass	Al	Ca	Cr	Fe	K	Mg	Mn	Na	Ni	P	S	Si	Ti
PERK 3 bottom quench xl	4.08	15.05	0.46	16.19	0.78	1.74	0.18	0.60	0.47	0.00	0.12	20.34	0.38
PERK 3 bptpm glass	6.35	6.55	0.02	4.85	0.90	1.82	0.00	4.21	0.00	0.00	1.43	28.63	0.31
PERK 3 side view 1/2 way	7.61	10.78	0.00	5.21	0.84	1.59	0.00	1.47	0.00	0.00	0.26	26.10	1.12
PERK 3 side view black glass	10.43	10.67	0.02	5.03	0.58	1.17	0.01	1.37	0.02	0.09	0.19	24.51	0.74
PERK 3 side view black glass	10.43	10.85	0.16	6.84	0.53	1.04	0.00	1.16	0.00	0.31	0.27	22.99	1.03
PERK 3 side view bottom area	7.06	8.83	0.00	3.76	0.95	1.28	0.17	1.27	0.07	0.06	0.36	28.59	1.22
Perk 7-1a crystals	15.34	9.24	0.00	2.11	0.08	0.06	0.00	1.50	0.07	0.07	0.43	23.72	0.71
Perk 7-1b alumina layer	42.43	2.72	0.00	1.22	0.48	0.57	0.27	0.55	0.31	0.37	0.17	4.78	0.00
Perk B 1 glass	1.48	1.73	0.00	15.95	2.33	0.21	7.99	0.92	0.12	0.38	0.00	10.00	21.85
Perk B 2	6.09	6.97	0.00	35.52	0.35	1.73	0.00	0.38	0.00	0.29	0.14	12.97	0.38
Perk C draping	8.74	12.41	0.00	10.25	0.26	5.18	0.03	0.45	0.00	0.15	0.07	19.26	1.02
Perk I amph	9.62	13.70	0.02	6.99	0.69	3.79	0.36	0.33	0.00	0.10	0.20	20.12	1.11
Perk I rock plag	17.35	10.63	0.00	1.83	0.44	0.38	0.13	1.29	0.34	0.29	0.06	21.34	0.07
Perk III quench Ca-Fe olv	2.39	20.49	0.00	19.10	0.00	2.49	0.00	0.74	0.00	0.02	0.07	16.83	0.67
Perk III quench plag	13.42	8.48	0.14	3.34	0.19	0.56	0.00	2.74	0.29	0.20	0.10	24.36	0.18
Perk III vug fill	4.51	13.67	0.00	7.36	0.63	6.46	0.63	0.54	0.00	0.21	0.38	22.73	0.00
Perk Mag Fract 3	4.52	8.32	0.10	39.08	0.23	1.68	0.00	1.08	0.06	0.04	0.11	10.44	1.28
Trench 1, PERK J clast brighter area	5.24	28.03	0.17	2.09	0.22	3.50	0.00	1.12	0.04	0.11	0.30	18.03	0.46
Trench 1, PERK J clast composition -CaCO ₃	5.48	45.27	0.00	1.09	0.56	1.76	0.00	2.45	0.00	0.02	1.00	7.30	0.00
Trench 1, PERK J glassy rim on clast	11.76	13.67	0.31	2.87	1.56	3.84	0.00	4.57	0.00	0.24	1.28	16.30	0.96
Trench 1, PERK J white area	8.46	38.03	0.00	0.43	0.07	0.50	0.00	0.43	0.00	0.00	10.63	1.21	0.03
Trench 1, PERK J white stuff	9.34	33.34	0.20	0.44	0.31	1.01	0.08	0.44	0.02	0.00	10.34	2.73	0.39
AVG	9.64	14.97	0.07	8.71	0.59	1.93	0.45	1.35	0.08	0.13	1.27	17.42	1.54

Table S6. SEM-EDS oxide abundances for spherules and meltglass from Trench 1 and the Vee deposit.

Object	#	SiO ₂	CaO	Al ₂ O ₃	FeO	TiO ₂	MgO	Na ₂ O	K ₂ O	
Sph Perk G area F tiny hollow sphere		59.43	3.73	26.01	3.02	0.10	3.15	2.00	2.57	This study
Sph Perk G sphere 50um		60.42	1.53	27.52	1.87	1.02	1.65	3.27	2.71	This study
Sph Perk G Sphere B		42.70	22.67	21.00	3.21	1.20	5.97	2.43	0.81	This study
Sph Perk G sphere D		43.56	16.48	25.15	4.31	2.68	3.37	2.71	1.75	This study
Sph Perk Spheres 56		57.76	23.91	7.92	6.96	1.17	1.32	0.73	0.23	This study
Sph Spher 37		63.28	16.85	7.93	3.97	5.60	1.86	0.08	0.43	This study
Sph Sphere 41		40.26	30.33	13.74	10.49	1.12	4.06	0.00	0.00	This study
Sph Sphere 53		24.86	36.11	18.11	12.50	3.55	3.26	0.87	0.73	This study
Perk spherules	8	49.03	18.95	18.42	5.79	2.06	3.08	1.51	1.15	
MG PERK 3 bottom quench xl		44.24	21.41	7.85	21.16	0.64	2.93	0.82	0.95	This study
MG PERK 3 bpttpm glass		61.90	9.26	12.13	6.31	0.52	3.06	5.73	1.09	This study
MG PERK 3 side view 1/2 way		56.13	15.16	14.45	6.74	1.87	2.66	1.99	1.01	This study
MG PERK 3 side view black glass		49.92	15.41	20.01	8.93	1.74	1.74	1.59	0.65	This study
MG PERK 3 side view black glass		52.83	15.04	19.85	6.52	1.24	1.95	1.86	0.70	This study
MG PERK 3 side view bottom area		61.97	12.51	13.51	4.90	2.06	2.15	1.73	1.16	This study
MG Perk 7-1a crystals		51.37	13.09	29.36	2.74	1.20	0.10	2.04	0.10	This study
MG Perk 7-1b alumina layer		10.44	3.88	81.78	1.60	0.00	0.96	0.76	0.59	This study
MG Perk B 1 glass		24.32	2.75	3.18	23.31	41.44	0.40	1.41	3.19	This study
MG Perk B 2		27.98	9.84	11.62	46.08	0.64	2.90	0.51	0.42	This study
MG Perk C draping		41.43	17.45	16.61	13.25	1.71	8.63	0.61	0.31	This study
MG Perk G area C dark		52.91	15.42	16.39	5.94	1.31	5.92	1.93	0.18	This study
MG Perk I amph		43.58	19.41	18.39	9.10	1.87	6.36	0.45	0.84	This study
MG Perk I rock plag		46.28	15.07	33.22	2.38	0.12	0.64	1.76	0.54	This study
MG Perk III quench Ca-Fe olv		36.00	28.67	4.52	24.55	1.12	4.13	1.00	0.00	This study
MG Perk III quench plag		52.75	12.01	25.67	4.35	0.30	0.94	3.74	0.23	This study
MG Perk III vug fill		49.65	19.53	8.71	9.67	0.00	10.93	0.74	0.77	This study
MG Perk Mag Fract 3		22.46	11.71	8.59	50.56	2.15	2.80	1.46	0.28	This study
MG Tr1,PERK J white stuff		7.88	63.06	23.85	0.76	0.88	2.26	0.80	0.50	This study
MG Trench 1, PERK J clast brighter area		39.08	39.73	10.02	2.72	0.78	5.88	1.53	0.27	This study
MG Trench 1, PERK J clast composition - CaCO ₃		15.99	64.89	10.62	1.44	0.00	2.99	3.38	0.69	This study
MG Trench 1, PERK J glassy rim on clast		36.36	19.93	23.17	3.84	1.66	6.64	6.42	1.96	This study
MG Trench 1, PERK J white area		3.50	72.04	21.64	0.74	0.07	1.11	0.78	0.11	This study
Perk meltglass	23	38.65	22.49	18.92	11.20	2.75	3.40	1.87	0.72	
Anthro spherules (n=167)	167	72.09	7.57	1.70	0.21	0.03	0.97	2.31	0.50	Niyoki, 2011
Impact spherules		48.31	9.24	13.67	15.27	2.32	6.84	1.81	0.32	Niyoki, 2011
Microtektites		68.59	3.24	15.33	5.42	0.84	4.66	0.66	1.00	Niyoki, 2011

Table S8. Source publications for fly ash data in the main manuscript.

Publications with fly ash elemental abundances					
Acosta et al., 1997	Spain	Nataraja et al., 2007	India	Shoumkova et al., 2006	Bulgaria
Bhatty et al., 2001	US (IL)	Nugteren et al., 2009	Netherlands	Sivakumar et al., 2009	India
Chandra et al., 2009	India	Oymael et al., 2007	China	Snelson et al., 2007	UK
Gao et al., 2004	China	Oymael et al., 2007	Germany	Sulc et al., 2009	Czechoslovakia
Giere, et al., 2003	Indiana	Oymael et al., 2007	Israel	This study	US (LA)
Gikunoo et al., 2004	Canada	Oymael et al., 2007	Jordan	This study	US (NJ)
Gikunoo et al., 2004	France	Oymael et al., 2007	US (CO)	Towler et al., 2002	Greece
Gikunoo et al., 2004	UK	Provis et al., 2009	Australia	Towler et al., 2002	Italy
Gikunoo et al., 2004	Japan	Rawlings et al., 2006	China	Towler et al., 2002	Netherlands
Gikunoo et al., 2004	US	Rawlings et al., 2006	Egypt	Towler et al., 2002	Spain
Jablonska et al., 2003	Poland	Rawlings et al., 2006	India	Uscinowicz et al., 2009	Poland
Jewell et al., 2009	US (KY)	Rawlings et al., 2006	Italy	Wang et al., 2003	Taiwan
Keyte et al., 2004	Australia	Rawlings et al., 2006	Poland	Ward et al., 2006	Australia
Keyte et al., 2004	New Zealand	Rawlings et al., 2006	Portugal	White et al., 2005	US (IA)
Mandal et al., 2006	India	Rawlings et al., 2006	Spain	Yamada et al., 2001	Japan
Marini et al., 2009	Estonia	Rawlings et al., 2006	Turkey	Yamada et al., 2001	Phillippines
Mckeen et al., 1998	US (NM)	Rawlings et al., 2006	US (IL)	Yamada et al., 2001	Thailand
Muriithi et al., 2009	S Africa	Rawlings et al., 2006	US (UT)	Yijin et al., 2004	China

Table S9. Fly ash elemental data from 5 continents compared with Perking spherules (Sph) and glass.

Normalized to Perkins	Cr	Ni	Mn	S	Ti	Ca	Na	Mg	Fe	Si	P	Al	K
Perk Sph+Glass (n=32)	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
Perkins (avg sed; n=5)	0.71	0.74	1.24	1.33	0.80	0.92	1.33	0.98	0.99	1.01	1.27	1.18	1.15
N. America (n=93)	0.49	0.48	0.51	0.08	0.30	0.53	0.65	1.14	2.06	1.03	2.05	0.97	1.39
Australia & NZ (n=22)	0.01	0.076	0.03	0.03	0.52	0.20	0.38	0.39	0.65	1.75	2.87	1.69	1.19
Africa & MidEast (n=6)	0.19	0.071	0.02	0.65	0.32	0.94	0.59	1.44	1.02	1.19	0.59	0.98	0.73
Asia (n=69)	0.00	0.075	0.03	0.03	0.14	0.31	0.49	0.53	0.64	1.64	0.06	1.78	1.46
Europe (n=77)	0.01	0.073	0.07	0.06	0.33	0.43	0.50	0.70	0.94	1.43	1.28	1.52	2.80
Fly ash average (n=304)	0.23	0.25	0.31	0.35	0.40	0.55	0.65	0.86	1.05	1.34	1.34	1.35	1.45
Original values	Cr	Ni	Mn	S	Ti	Ca	Na	Mg	Fe	Si	P	Al	K
Perkins MSp+Glass	0.16	0.13	0.60	5.60	2.32	22.52	2.16	3.15	16.05	30.36	0.16	15.66	1.12
N. America	0.08	0.06	0.31	0.42	0.69	12.00	1.40	3.58	33.02	31.29	0.33	15.26	1.56
Australia, New Zealand	0.00	0.010	0.02	0.14	1.20	4.59	0.82	1.23	10.51	53.19	0.46	26.50	1.33
Africa, MidEast	0.03	0.009	0.01	3.63	0.74	21.08	1.28	4.54	16.38	35.99	0.09	15.38	0.82
Asia	0.00	0.009	0.02	0.19	0.32	7.00	1.07	1.67	10.29	49.85	0.01	27.95	1.63
Europe	0.00	0.009	0.05	0.32	0.77	9.78	1.09	2.20	15.16	43.47	0.21	23.81	3.14
Perkins (avg sediment)	0.20	0.09	0.74	4.65	1.84	20.66	2.48	3.09	15.93	30.62	0.20	18.45	1.02

Table S10. Specifications from the online Earth Impact Effects Program^{1,2}

Comet diameter = 350 m; largest frag = 100 m, expands 365 times
 Density = 250 kg/m³ = SL-9 ice, pancake => 1/250 = 5 kg/m³
 Impactor velocity = 30 km/s
 Entry angle = 45° => 45° for fragments
 Residual velocity = 0.975 km/s
 Target density = 2500 kg/m³
 Energy, Mt, atmosphere = 603 Mt
 Impact energy = 0.64 Mt

Initial breakup = 108 km
 Airburst altitude = none; forms a shallow crater
 Transient crater = 290 x 102
 Final crater = 362 x 77
 Crater field = 2.9 x 2.1 km
 Breccia layer 35.7 m
 Impact recurrence = 19,000 years

Table S11. Material specifications for the Autodyn hydrocode model.

Material Name - Earth	
Equation of State	Tillotson
Reference density	2.75000E+00 (g/cm ³)
Parameter A	1.80000E+07 (kPa)
Parameter B	1.80000E+07 (kPa)
Parameter a	5.00000E-01 (none)
Parameter b	1.30000E+00 (none)
Parameter alpha	5.00000E+00 (none)
Parameter beta	5.00000E+00 (none)
Parameter e0	1.60000E-01 (J/kg)
Parameter es	3.50000E-03 (J/kg)
Parameter esd	1.80000E-02 (J/kg)
Reference Temperature	2.73000E+02 (K)
Specific Heat	9.20000E+02 (J/kgK)
Thermal Conductivity	5.00000E+00 (J/mKs)
Strength	von Mises
Shear Modulus	7.00000E+07 (kPa)
Yield Stress	9.00000E+01 (kPa)
Failure	None
Erosion	None
Material Cutoffs	-
Maximum Expansion	1.00000E-01 (none)
Minimum Density Factor	1.00000E-04 (none)
Minimum Density Factor (SPH)	2.00000E-01 (none)
Maximum Density Factor (SPH)	3.00000E+00 (none)
Minimum Soundspeed	1.00000E-06 (m/s)
Maximum Soundspeed (SPH)	1.01000E+05 (m/s)
Maximum Temperature	1.01000E+20 (K)
Reference:	-
Material Name - AIR	

Equation of State	Ideal Gas
Reference density	1.22500E-03 (g/cm ³)
Gamma	1.40000E+00 (none)
Adiabatic constant	0.00000E+00 (none)
Pressure shift	0.00000E+00 (kPa)
Reference Temperature	2.88200E+02 (K)
Specific Heat	7.17600E+02 (J/kgK)
Thermal Conductivity	0.00000E+00 (J/mKs)
Strength	None
Failure	None
Erosion	None
Material Cutoffs	-
Maximum Expansion	1.00000E-01 (none)
Minimum Density Factor	1.00000E-04 (none)
Minimum Density Factor (SPH)	2.00000E-01 (none)
Maximum Density Factor (SPH)	3.00000E+00 (none)
Minimum Soundspeed	1.00000E-02 (m/s)
Maximum Soundspeed (SPH)	1.01000E+05 (m/s)
Maximum Temperature	1.01000E+20 (K)
Reference:	"Thermodynamic and Transport Properties of Fluids, SI Units" GFC Rogers, YR Mayhew

Material Name - Comet

Equation of State	Tillotson
Reference density	5.00000E-03 (g/cm ³)
Parameter A	1.25000E+06 (kPa)
Parameter B	7.50000E+05 (kPa)
Parameter a	5.00000E-01 (none)
Parameter b	1.30000E+00 (none)
Parameter alpha	5.00000E+00 (none)
Parameter beta	5.00000E+00 (none)
Parameter e0	1.10000E+07 (J/kg)
Parameter es	3.20000E+08 (J/kg)
Parameter esd	1.60000E+09 (J/kg)
Reference Temperature	5.00000E+01 (K)
Specific Heat	1.00000E+03 (J/kgK)
Thermal Conductivity	5.00000E+00 (J/mKs)
Strength	von Mises
Shear Modulus	7.50000E+02 (kPa)
Yield Stress	8.70000E+00 (kPa)
Failure	Hydro (Pmin)

Hydro Tensile Limit	-2.75000E+04 (kPa)
Reheal	No
Crack Softening	No
Stochastic failure	No
Erosion	None
Material Cutoffs	-
Maximum Expansion	5.00000E-01 (none)
Minimum Density Factor	1.00000E-04 (none)
Minimum Density Factor (SPH)	2.00000E-01 (none)
Maximum Density Factor (SPH)	3.00000E+00 (none)
Minimum Soundspeed	1.00000E-06 (m/s)
Maximum Soundspeed (SPH)	1.01000E+05 (m/s)
Maximum Temperature	1.01000E+20 (K)
Reference:	-

Material Name - Trees #1

Equation of State	Tillotson
Reference density	1.00000E-01 (g/cm3)
Parameter A	1.25000E+06 (kPa)
Parameter B	7.50000E+05 (kPa)
Parameter a	5.00000E-01 (none)
Parameter b	1.30000E+00 (none)
Parameter alpha	5.00000E+00 (none)
Parameter beta	5.00000E+00 (none)
Parameter e0	1.10000E+07 (J/kg)
Parameter es	3.20000E+08 (J/kg)
Parameter esd	1.60000E+09 (J/kg)
Reference Temperature	5.00000E+01 (K)
Specific Heat	1.00000E+03 (J/kgK)
Thermal Conductivity	5.00000E+00 (J/mKs)
Strength	von Mises
Shear Modulus	3.00000E+01 (kPa)
Yield Stress	3.00000E+00 (kPa)
Failure	Hydro (Pmin)
Hydro Tensile Limit	-2.75000E+04 (kPa)
Reheal	No
Crack Softening	No
Stochastic failure	No
Erosion	None
Material Cutoffs	-
Maximum Expansion	5.00000E-01 (none)
Minimum Density Factor	1.00000E-04 (none)

Minimum Density Factor (SPH)	2.00000E-01 (none)
Maximum Density Factor (SPH)	3.00000E+00 (none)
Minimum Soundspeed	1.00000E-06 (m/s)
Maximum Soundspeed (SPH)	1.01000E+05 (m/s)
Maximum Temperature	1.01000E+20 (K)
Reference:	-

Material Name - Trees #2

Equation of State	Tillotson
Reference density	1.00000E-01 (g/cm3)
Parameter A	1.25000E+06 (kPa)
Parameter B	7.50000E+05 (kPa)
Parameter a	5.00000E-01 (none)
Parameter b	1.30000E+00 (none)
Parameter alpha	5.00000E+00 (none)
Parameter beta	5.00000E+00 (none)
Parameter e0	1.10000E+07 (J/kg)
Parameter es	3.20000E+08 (J/kg)
Parameter esd	1.60000E+09 (J/kg)
Reference Temperature	5.00000E+01 (K)
Specific Heat	1.00000E+03 (J/kgK)
Thermal Conductivity	5.00000E+00 (J/mKs)
Strength	von Mises
Shear Modulus	3.00000E+01 (kPa)
Yield Stress	3.00000E+00 (kPa)
Failure	Hydro (Pmin)
Hydro Tensile Limit	-2.75000E+04 (kPa)
Reheal	No
Crack Softening	No
Stochastic failure	No
Erosion	None
Material Cutoffs	-
Maximum Expansion	5.00000E-01 (none)
Minimum Density Factor	1.00000E-04 (none)
Minimum Density Factor (SPH)	2.00000E-01 (none)
Maximum Density Factor (SPH)	3.00000E+00 (none)
Minimum Soundspeed	1.00000E-06 (m/s)
Maximum Soundspeed (SPH)	1.01000E+05 (m/s)
Maximum Temperature	1.01000E+20 (K)
Reference:	-

Material Name - Trees #3

Equation of State	Tillotson
Reference density	1.00000E-01 (g/cm ³)
Parameter A	1.25000E+06 (kPa)
Parameter B	7.50000E+05 (kPa)
Parameter a	5.00000E-01 (none)
Parameter b	1.30000E+00 (none)
Parameter alpha	5.00000E+00 (none)
Parameter beta	5.00000E+00 (none)
Parameter e0	1.10000E+07 (J/kg)
Parameter es	3.20000E+08 (J/kg)
Parameter esd	1.60000E+09 (J/kg)
Reference Temperature	5.00000E+01 (K)
Specific Heat	1.00000E+03 (J/kgK)
Thermal Conductivity	5.00000E+00 (J/mKs)
Strength	von Mises
Shear Modulus	3.00000E+01 (kPa)
Yield Stress	3.00000E+00 (kPa)
Failure	Hydro (Pmin)
Hydro Tensile Limit	-2.75000E+04 (kPa)
Reheal	No
Crack Softening	No
Stochastic failure	No
Erosion	None
Material Cutoffs	-
Maximum Expansion	5.00000E-01 (none)
Minimum Density Factor	1.00000E-04 (none)
Minimum Density Factor (SPH)	2.00000E-01 (none)
Maximum Density Factor (SPH)	3.00000E+00 (none)
Minimum Soundspeed	1.00000E-06 (m/s)
Maximum Soundspeed (SPH)	1.01000E+05 (m/s)
Maximum Temperature	1.01000E+20 (K)

METHODS

Spherules, carbon micro-spherules, glass-like carbon, and meltglass

Samples were processed using a previously published protocol³⁻⁶. After size-sorting using multiple screens ranging from 4.75 mm to 53 μ m (certified by the American Society for Testing and Materials), cross-sectioned and whole micro-spherules and meltglass were examined using SEM-EDS by seven coauthors (J.P.K., T.E.B., J.H.W., J.C.W., M.A.L., A.W., and A.V.A.). Results by various coauthors were statistically the same. Standard techniques were followed for all analytical methods.

Optical Microscopy

Selected sedimentary grains were initially examined with optical microscopy, using magnifications ranging from 04x to 100x, to identify and categorize various particles of interest, including microspherules, carbon spherules, and mineral grains. Both transmitted and reflected light microscopy were employed, with epi-illumination used to examine the surface details of samples following standard petrographic techniques.

Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM)

SEM images were acquired using various JEOL-6000 SEM systems in low-vacuum mode and a ThermoFisher Apreo 2 SEM microscope with a cathodoluminescence (CL) detector to obtain high-resolution images of particles and their surfaces and to perform elemental analyses. Energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) was employed to determine elemental compositions and ratios of grains.

Cathodoluminescence (CL)

CL imaging was used to examine the internal structures of quartz grains, particularly to identify areas of recrystallization and distinguish between the grains' crystalline and amorphous regions. Following standard procedures, the analysis was performed using a Monarc CL Detector (Gatan; Pleasanton, CA).

Neutron Activation Analysis

Sediment samples were analyzed for elemental abundances using INAA by ActLabs, Canada. Analyses were performed for 56 elements, using bulk sediment samples of ~50 g each.

Data Analysis

Quantitative analyses of elemental compositions were performed using standardized EDS procedures. Crystallographic data from EBSD were processed using "PRIAS," an acronym for "Pattern Region of Interest Analysis System," to generate orientation maps and pole figures. Using ThermoFisher Noran System 7 software, image analyses were conducted to measure particle sizes and quantify structural features observed in the SEM, TEM, and CL images.

Temperature Estimations

Melting temperatures for various materials were estimated based on known equilibrium melting points of minerals and compounds identified within the samples. These were used to estimate the minimum temperatures reached during the airburst/impact event.

Argon-argon dating ($^{40}\text{Ar}/^{39}\text{Ar}$).

$^{40}\text{Ar}/^{39}\text{Ar}$ dating was performed at the University of Alaska Fairbanks Geochronology Laboratory. Impact spherules were separated from a hand sample by dissolving the carbonate matrix with 3N nitric acid at room temperature for 4 hours, which helped to disaggregate the material. The material was washed with deionized (DI) water, sonicated for 1 hour in DI, and rinsed 10 times with DI before being dried in a vacuum oven at 60°C. The material was sieved to >50 μm , and spherules were picked under a light microscope to produce a clean separate. This sample was irradiated at the Oregon State University TRIGA reactor in the Cadmium-Lined in-Core Irradiation Tube (CLICIT) for 6 hours at 1 MeV equivalent flux. Irradiated samples were step-heated from 0.2 to 12% laser power using a Teledyne CO₂ laser, and the resulting gas was cleaned using a LN₂ cooled stainless steel trap, two SAES GP50 getters, and an SAES CapaciTorr HV100 ZAO getter for 5 minutes. The gas was inlet into the Isotopx NGX multi-collector mass spectrometer and measured using an all-Faraday configuration with ATONA amplifiers for 20 minutes. Data acquisition and reduction were done with Pychron, and ages were calculated using co-irradiated Fish Canyon Tuff (FCT) sanidine as a flux monitor. Ages were corrected for argon from air and irradiation-related sources.

Magnetic Profiles Measurement

Magnetic profiles were initially intended to be measured using an unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV). However, due to a crash during a reconnaissance flight, the UAV was rendered unusable. As a result, the measurements were conducted using a conventional handheld setup. Two identical fluxgate magnetometers were employed: one for a stationary base station and the other for profile measurements. The profiles were measured along 100-meter transects at two locations near the crater (Figure 28). The fluxgate magnetometers recorded the X , Y , and Z components of the geomagnetic field at a sampling frequency of 62.5 samples per second. GPS data and status parameters were recorded for each measurement point. The total magnetic field vector was calculated from these components as:

$$T = \sqrt{X^2 + Y^2 + Z^2}$$

where X, Y, Z are the components of the magnetic field measured with fluxgate. Corrections for diurnal variations were applied using data from the base station.

Bayesian code for P-sequence

```
Options()  
{  
  Resolution=5;  
  Curve="IntCal20";  
};  
Plot()
```

```

{
Outlier_Model("General",Exp(1,-10,3),U(0,4),"t");
P_Sequence("Perkins",0.8,10)
{
Boundary();

R_Date("D-AMS 037679",25062,98){z=112.5;Outlier("General",1)};
R_Date("D-AMS 043969",10775,43){z=67.5;Outlier("General",1)};
C_Date("Pt/MSp/Glass                                     peak",(1950-
12785),50){z=67.5;Outlier("General",1);color="green"};
C_Date("Early                                     Archaic                                     Point",(1950-
9000),1000){z=48.0;Outlier("General",1);color="orange"};
C_Date("Late                                     Woodland                                     Point",(1950-
1250),250){z=7.5;Outlier("General",1);color="orange"};

Boundary();
};
};

```

Bayesian code for calibrated dates

```

Options()
{
Resolution=5;
Curve="IntCal20";
};
Plot("Six Perkins dates")
{
R_Date("Pond, UGAMS-67350",16850,65);
R_Date("Pond, UGAMS-68226",12100,40);
C_Date("YDB age range",(1950-12785),50);
R_Date("Trench 1, D-AMS 043969",10775,43);
R_Date("Pond, UGAMS-68225",10660,35);
R_Date("Vee, D-AMS 037682",10554,42);
R_Date("Pond, UGAMS-67351",8970,35);
};
};

```

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